

MAY 2021

HUMANITARIAN PARTNERSHIPS AND NETWORKS WEEKS

EVENT REPORT

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HUMANITARIAN OPERATIONS, GENDER, VULNERABILITY AND SECURITY AGENCIES

Outcomes and After-Action Report

Proposal

Who we are:

The InterAgency Institute is dedicated to research security issues, such as border control, interagency schemes, and cooperation frameworks, especially complex scenarios, policy building, and governance. Our proposal aims at enhancing collaboration in developing ideas for a more effective multistakeholder approach in dealing with migration crises, adopting a people-centered approach and a gender perspective. Our focus for the HNPW 2021 is the Venezuelan refugee crisis, especially the experiences and demands of women, LGBTQIA +and children.

Our main invitee is Plataforma CIPÓ, an independent policy research institute dedicated to climate and environmental issues, as well as correlate issues such as migration, including in the Amazon basin. We also are looking for partners inside the networks already established within HNPW.

Theme: Humanitarian Operations, Gender Vulnerability, and Security Agencies

- 2 sessions remotely organized as Zoom Meetings.
- Streaming (InterAgency Institute Youtube channel).
- Captioning or International Sign Language will be considered to facilitate the diffusion of the event (Youtube channel).
- Public Meetings.

Specific details:

Session 1

- I. Time frame: Wed, 28 April 2021 at 13h-15h30 UTC
- II. Priority topic sessions: Interactive sessions to provide updates on progress made since 2020 (for HNPW 2020 topics) and to advance the topic.
- III. Audience: Global (students from USSG, researchers; policymakers and practitioners)
- IV. Method:
 - a. Part 1 = Host opening + Moderator presentation of rules and panelists + 8-12 min for each panelist (4 in total)

- b. Part 2 = Interaction with the public - breakout sessions guided by a question to be answered.
- c. Part 3 = Results from breakout sessions moderators + comments from the panelists + wrap up from moderator and host.

V. Language: English

VI. Participants:

Dr Sabrina Medeiros, InterAgency Institute (IA), Portugal (host)

Ms Beatriz Duarte, IA and Coimbra University (moderator)

Panelists:

Dr Ana Luiza Paiva, Army Command and Staff College, Brazil

Dr Pichamon Yeophantong, UNSW, Australia

Dr Adriana Erthal Abdenur, Plataforma CIPÓ, Brazil

Ms Dana Y. B. Romero, Senior Gender Adviser, IASC Gender Standby Capacity Project (GenCap)

Breakout Sessions Moderators:

Dr Lygia Hryniewicz, Germany

Dr Silvana Schimanski, Brazil

Ms Flavia Osorio, Brazil/Colombia

Ms Carolina Ambinder, Brazil

Session 2

- I. Time frame: Wed, 5 May 2021 at 13h-15h30 UTC
- II. Technical meetings: Interactive simulation to address a specific technical issue (gender-related mechanisms of external control).

- III. Audience: Latin America + Iberia Peninsula (Portugal + Spain) + Community of Portuguese Language Countries - CPLP (Portuguese-speaking countries, including those in Africa).
- IV. Method: Virtual Simulation
- V. Languages: Spanish / Portuguese
- VI. Participants:

IA participants:

Dr Ana Paula Rodriguez, Spain/Brazil(host)

Dr Cintiene Mendes, Brazil (moderator)

Group's moderators:

Dr Sabrina Medeiros, Portugal

Dr Daniele Dionísio, Brazil

Dr Ana luiza Bravo e Paiva, Brazil

Dr Luzia Becker, Germany

Dr Lygia Hryniewicz , Germany

Ms Ana Beatriz Duarte, Portugal

Ms Flávia Seidel Osorio, Brazil

Invitees:

Luísa Falcão, Plataforma Cipó, Brazil

Arnaldo Ibrahim, Federal Police, Brazil

Sandra Becker, UFRJ, Brazil

Marina Aragão, American Development Foundation, Brazil

Rachel Castilho, UERJ, Brazil

Abstract:

Humanitarian actions aimed at supporting migrant populations involve situations of vulnerability, often featuring violations of rights. In institutionally deteriorated systems, groups of affected individuals crossing international borders receive different types of treatment from the various stakeholders involved, which calls for qualified policies to overcome barriers to assistance, especially to women, LGBTQI+ and children. Latin America's recent experience with the Venezuela refugee crisis, including the movement of large numbers of Venezuelans to Brazilian and Colombian cities (as either final or intermediate destinations), shows that, despite local innovations, greater attention is needed to women, LGBTQI+ and children.

The Acolhida Operation, launched in 2018 by the Brazilian government with support from civil society, private sector, and international organizations, has had a significant impact in terms of developing coordination instruments to facilitate cooperation among military, security, social and civil society institutions. As with any complex environment, the humanitarian operations in this context are also marked by both improvements and failures.

Recently, one of the humanitarian shelters dedicated to women, LGBTQI+, and children in the border state of Roraima (Brazil) was invaded by the Federal Police, without previous notification or court order. In addition, the COVID-19 pandemic also poses new challenges in addressing humanitarian contingencies, and the sanitary conditions of the Acolhida Operation have been conditioned by an upholding security approach.

This environment may create other adverse conditions for the wellbeing of the migrants, like conflicts of conduct, in which the rules of engagement are either incipient or non-existent. Women, LGBTQI+ and children are especially affected, and thus, more attention is needed in terms of understanding and improving how institutions and representatives behave and how interaction should be governed in the field.

Objectives – Our objective is to discuss ways to govern the interaction between local agencies and external observation, military and civilian; to build communication schemes; and to promote multistakeholder incremental policy-building.

Target audience – our target audience comprises students, researchers, and practitioners (from national, local, international organizations, NGOs).

Expected outcomes - In the first activity, we are proposing a conceptual and governance lens to offer guidelines for addressing the needs of women, LGBTQI+ and children. In the second session, we will build a simulation in order to propose a framework informed by the views of different stakeholders.

Keywords: Migration, Crisis, Humanitarian, Interagency, Gender, Venezuela, Refugees

Sessions Recording

Session 1 Part 1:

https://youtu.be/7t1H_1YYPe8

Session 1 Part 2:

<https://youtu.be/3Qy1gCE4AOs>

Session 2 Part 1:

https://youtu.be/1hHhz_SBDpw

Session 2 Part 2:

https://youtu.be/0QLe_GbXw_o

Sessions Participation

Session 1 - Executive Summary

Climate Change and the Venezuelan Refugee Crisis - Dr. Adriana Abdenur

- When we look at refugees, we observe on the Brazil-Venezuela border and what we find is that the Venezuelan refugees, especially groups like women and children and indigenous refugees, comprise the majority of those who are in Pacaraima and are extremely vulnerable to climate change, not only in their places of origin but also throughout the migratory process and the refuge process.
- Two questions: what risks climate change poses in the context of the Venezuelan refugee crisis does and; what measures can be taken by stakeholders what best practices can we identify, especially those that are relevant for women in indigenous groups as well as children.
- Climate change, along with inadequate infrastructure, has contributed to the Venezuelan refugee crisis and the deterioration of energy infrastructure, but also, extreme weather events and environmental degradation have contributed towards, for instance, the migration of the indigenous communities to other countries in the region.
- Climate change threatens food and water security, making means of subsistence even more challenging not only for a population that has been made even more vulnerable due to the COVID pandemic but also for the host communities.
- The vast majority of Venezuelans who arrive in Brazil is highly susceptible to climate change, especially due to the intensification of heat and, on the other hand, during the rainy season, the increasing unpredictability and intensity of rains. In addition, Roraima is very susceptible right now to environmental degradation.
- Neither Pacaraima nor Boa Vista has adequate drainage systems - the military can assist because they do have the capability in their engineering core.

- How to mainstream a climate perspective across the entire process of voluntary resettlement which we call into the interior disaster within the scope of Acolhida Operation.

The Acolhida Operation Structure - Dr. Ana Luiza Bravo

- Operação Acolhida (since 2018) has provided to be a unique opportunity to test the new Brazilian migration law of 2017.
- The complexity of receiving migrants throughout the border. It requires strong integration and cooperation frameworks, especially on civil-military coordination. There are over 90 agencies involved in this Operation that include governmental organizations, civilian and military agencies, international agencies. NGOs and private companies.
- The logistics issues are the responsibility of the Ministry of Defence; that is why the Brazilian army, due to its presence in the Amazon, became the coordinator of the humanitarian logistic task force.
- Brazilian military doctrine has a relatively recent interagency operations scheme - the military and the civil agencies started to work together since the World Cup and the Olympic games (2014 and 2016).
- Since 2004 Brazil is involved in humanitarian operations like peacekeeping, but it is the first time we are planning and coordinating all the steps of a humanitarian operation in our country, in our territories - that's the reason there are so many things that are still in progress.

The Gender perspective of the Refugee Crisis in Latin American countries - Ms. Dana Romero

- The Latin American region has faced an increase of criminality and violence, narco-trafficking, trafficking in persons, also affecting most women and girls, and also increased the level of inequality and discrimination women and girls from Venezuela have been facing.

- Gender-based violence in several countries, in addition to a conflict situation in countries like Colombia, for example, and also the insecurity and displacement, which has been exacerbating in the region because of climate change.
- The importance of the participation of women as part of the prevention of conflict but also as part of the initiatives in terms of remediation and negotiation of conflict in our region.
- It's important that we also develop the good practice cases of when gender sensitivity is actually seen and where gender analysis has actually worked to help make humanitarian operations more effective and more nuanced in terms of their engagement with women, as well as with other marginalized and vulnerable groups.
- An integrated process of data collection, fact-finding, and knowledge production, as a result, is central to accountability and transparency.
- The indigenous women in the amazon have constituted networks, and some of these span different countries to exchange ideas, and they range from, you know, climate adaptation through seed collection and storage.
- This incipient knowledge has not been mobilized very much within the context of the refugee crisis. The first step would be to carry out a survey of the refugee women, including indigenous ones, to see how they tend to respond and what their ideas are for me, both mitigation and adaptation.
- How women and men use power electricity is very different, and so in a humanitarian or refugee camp.

Experiences from Myanmar and Bangladesh Refugee Crisis - Dr. Pichamon Yeophantong

- Women are victims but are also agents of change - multiple roles that women can play must be visible.
- Women also face different types of threats and risks: when looking for their communities, dealing with the leaderships, taking care of their families, or leading social advocacy.

- Enablers of inclusion are connected to the social norms, sexual and reproductive health, and various other multiple layers where women are affected. It is important to recognize individual and context-specific needs (intersectionality).
- Establish social and collective identities and ownership of solutions.
- Access to information and knowledge creation. Accountability and transparency. Reflexivity and context sensitivity. Focus on meaningful participation - not only desegregated data points and numbers.
- Focus humanitarian responses as a process, not only outcomes. Good practice cases are very useful.

Results

1) MIRO

Findings from the interaction promoted throughout the two days of the event can be seen on the MIRO platform, as shown below.

[https://miro.com/app/board/o9J_lJBs2Yw=/
/](https://miro.com/app/board/o9J_lJBs2Yw=/)

From the first day of interaction, the final remarks wrap up:

The image shows a Miro board with six sticky notes. The notes are arranged in two rows. The top row has four notes, and the bottom row has two notes. The notes contain the following text:

- Colombia - many refugees but no support many women - lack of support - aids migrants star over - there is no capacity - capacities to help migrants are not there - low governmental capacities do provide documentation for the migrants mainly women - for example, financial opportunities etc**
- We have to acknowledge in the borders in Latin American
There are Convention - There is not political involvement or commitment - crises rises and we still unable to establish capacities - we have powerful women fighting against these issue -
There is lack of capacity and lack of accountability
There is not a good response about this if there is not a guidance or policies
who is crossing the borders - need motivation to face this issue -
It is very difficult to get attention from the government - what should we do to create an agenda taking account on gender an their vulnerabilities?**
- Gender inclusion - reffugee in Lebanon - local communitie leader - support for the women and she communicated to all women - design the program: they give some tecnicl course - find relabel full capacity from the migrants - trust the program and apply with key people**
- characterization of women and children- infantilize women in many aspects, gender roles are quite different - better differentiation between capacities and vulnerabilities**
- Brazil: negative way - we have progress in legislation but not progress in gender issues - operation acolhida is interesting is a humanitarian objective and institution are still working, although the Government decided to other political decisions - what we need is interaction more in many political levels: ineract in horizontal and vertical level**
- political will? Do we have it? They need to increase investment in gender issues and more support on women organizations - we have capacity to respond about this migration crisis - but there is not economic resources on gender - we have to understand where the resources allocated. 20% of the activities are located on gender inequalities**

- Channels of communications need to be reinforced, so that was pretty clear that the decision-makers in the policy arena need to listen to the bottom side of the demands. The importance of communication between the government agencies and the other stakeholders.
- Bottom side of the demands. The importance of communication between the government agencies and the other stakeholders.
- Training workers in human rights in two ways: in a more practical way teaching people what their human rights are, and another in a more theoretical pattern, trying to make people conscious or make people more sensitive about the associated human rights.
- The need to have NGO advocacy more valued in the national dimension.
- The need to translate protocols to local language and make sure that they are feasible and what are the capabilities and capacities demanded.
- Role visibility and transparency: the need of being very specified determined what are the roles of each agent working in the operation.

- How to guarantee political and economic resources allocated to address and promote gender equality programming.

SURVEY:

Our survey about the most important elements to promoting interagency cooperation in the benefit of the protection of migrant populations when considering humanitarian operations and gender-related issues resulted on:

- Military-civilian coordination and a multistakeholder approach on social policies are more important; also, the relations between the international NGOs and the local ones as a factor of contribution to the humanitarian effectiveness.

Session 2 - Executive Summary

The session was built to promote interaction most part of the time, in the form of simulation. After the host and moderator presentations of the general objectives of the events and the method for the interactive session, the working groups would have to represent, in focal discussions moderated by the InterAgency Institute researchers, each one of the actors in their respective functions and proposing ideas for the interagency efficiency and incremental effectiveness.

The scheme below is a Perspective Circle Tool (NXplorers) where the agencies to be simulated are the main 4 actors in the Acolhida Operation case dealing with Venezuelan Refugees, especially the most vulnerable ones such as the women, children, and indigenous.

Scamper						
S	C	A	M	P	E	R
What should be replaced ?	How to combine actions in a coordinated way?	How to adapt actions to an existing reality?	What needs to be modified ?	What new proposals can be suggested?	What can we eliminate to avoid risks and errors?	What new arrangements can be implemented?

Based on the results achieved from the first session, in the center of the scheme built in the interactive online tool (Miro), the agencies represented had the responsibility of offering insights as answers using the SCAMPER method (NXplorer).

Simulated Actors

The simulated actors were: Armed Forces, Federal Police, UNHCR / NGO, and Ministry of Citizenship. The choice of actors in the simulation is due to the fact that they are active agencies throughout Acolhida Operation and, because they are also active, in the issue of women and children migrants.

The simulation was developed in 4 sessions using the SCAMPER tool, presented above with the questions to be solved or suggested based on the problem situation.

The actors represented by the groups should discuss, based on the agency's competence, situations such as: What should be replaced in the real situation, what could be combined in the coordination of actions, how to adapt actions to the real situation, what needs to be

changed, what are the suggested proposals, which to eliminate to avoid risks and errors, which new arrangements can be implemented. These questions are part of the SCAMPER tool and, before being used, session 1 was prepared; on the 28th, actions were discussed by the working group and the presentation of the panelists.

The combination of the methods used will enable us to verify the perspective circle, which is a tool that allows us to have a multiple and broad view about the object of analysis, thinking about different points of view and perceptions. In this way, the actors/agencies represented could compare their results and perspectives throughout the simulation, expanding the interagency work and sharing information, decisions, and political orientation for the benefit of migrants' rights.

Below is the MIRO image where the tools were used.

Simulation Results

We will present below the general information about what each agency has defined through the SCAMPER tool.

UNHCR/NGO

- One of the suggestions to be replaced by UNHCR's simulated view is the need for a review of the granting policies for refugees, carried out by CONARE in Brazil.
- There is a need to combine efforts between civil society and public officials, as well as to draw up plans for situations of a deeper crisis and a task force with UN agencies.
- Adapt operations to the cultures of the various ethnic groups and migrant peoples.
- Need for monitoring of interiorization, strategic planning for the interiorization process, and implementation of places for greater social integration.
- The UNHCR / NGO's proposals are part of the greater coordination of actions for the internalization of migrants, active participation of the Ministry of Citizenship, to facilitate dialogue and local actions, vaccination plan for populations with different cultures, and greater participation of the Federal Public Defender's Office in assistance of children.
- Some issues must be eliminated for better action. According to the UNHCR / NGO working group, permanent shelters should be permanently eliminated; it is necessary to eliminate and overcome the absence of public agents in the Operation and greater training and capacity building to eliminate sexual violence against women.
- One of the issues raised as a rearrangement is the centralization of Operation Acolhida with the Armed Forces. The rearrangement is part of the transfer of the operation process to civilians and responsible agencies.

ACNUR and NGO

Scamper Tool

S	C	A	M	P	E	R
What should be replaced ?	How to combine actions in a coordinated way?	How to adapt actions to an existing reality?	What needs to be modified ?	What new proposals can be suggested?	What can we eliminate to avoid risks and errors?	What new arrangements can be implemented?
<p>Review of the Refusal Policy for asylum applications by CONARE. Voting proposal signed by organizations.</p>	<p>ask force formation among UN organizations for reporting and diagnosis to make extraordinary requests</p> <p>individually identify vulnerable people and, together, seek regulation (documentation, which is the tip of the integration process and services) by other competent institutions</p> <p>coordination to think about the crisis of the crisis - at a time of pandemic, closed frontier >> street population generated by irregular entry (closed frontiers) and lack of documentation generates xenophobia</p> <p>Civil society has more to train public officials than the other way around. Training proposal.</p>	<p>adapt operations to the cultures of the various ethnic groups and migrant peoples.</p>	<p>follow-up of interns shelters as a space for integration with society</p> <p>modify the strategy with a greater focus on interiorization</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> coordinated nuclei of the operation from Roraima to the destination of the inmates to ensure safety and follow up later inclusion of Venezuelan Indians in vaccination plans. With prior consultation with traditional peoples (four ethnicities with different cultures regarding migration and vaccination, for example) Greater participation of the Ministry of Citizenship. The absence hinders dialogue and local actions Strengthening of the Federal Public Defender's Office to assist unaccompanied children. Increase in the number of day care centers and spaces within the shelters. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Eliminate the permanent nature of shelters that should be emergency Eliminate absence and rarity of the presence of public agentes training to eliminate risks of sexual violence 	<p>rethink the centralization of FFAA actions that hinder UN actions. Most difficult relationship since last year</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Military coordination has a deadline that the pandemic has extended. A process of decentralization and transition to civilians has already begun There is still a lack of definition of the agency's roles in the future Decentralization has been difficult and how it will work has not been achieved.

Federal Police

- As a suggestion by the group that represents the Federal Police: use the data segregation base (already collected) considering specific groups and whether it was a refuge or residence (greater bureaucracy)
- As a combined and coordinated action, they demonstrate the need and relevance of the Federal Public Defender and the condition attributed to children and adolescents.
- The issues to be adapted are the complexity of the Operation - several actors with various responsibilities, the problematic issue of the adolescents, and the adequacy of the FP's day today.
- As a proposal to modify actions, they cite problems across the country with internal migration and the abandonment of children, and the absence of the Public Defender's Office of the Union.
- As a proposal, the group that represented the Federal Police indicated the implementation of a permanent mechanism to report experiences and good practices among all the actors involved. Joint work on understanding and understanding of indigenous culture - Warao, indigenous and teenagers
- As a new proposal, the rational choice is based on the collection of information and knowledge-based, not only on the law.
- There was no proposal by the group for rearrangements in actions or institutional.

Federal Police

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Scamper Tool

S	C	A	M	P	E	R
What should be replaced?	How to combine actions in a coordinated way?	How to adapt actions to an existing reality?	What needs to be modified?	What new proposals can be suggested?	What can we eliminate to avoid risks and errors?	What new arrangements can be implemented?
Use the data segregation base (already collected) considering specific groups and whether it was a refuge or residence (greater bureaucracy)	Relevance of the Federal Public Defender's Office and the status attributed to children and adolescents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Complexity - multiple actors with multiple responsibilities · The problematic issue of adolescents · the adequacy of the daily life of the PF 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · issues across the country by internal migration · abandonment of children and guilt of the Public Defender of the Union 	Permanent mechanism for reporting experiences and good practices among all actors involved <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Warao, indigenous and teenagers 	As a new proposal, the rational choice based on the collection of information and knowledge based not only on the law	

Ministry of Citizenship

- The group does not include new suggestions in the document to be presented.
- As combined activities, the group that represented the Ministry of Citizenship indicated the need to develop courses for qualifying results, creating actions and activities for university extension, and raising awareness and instruction of the agents involved in the process.
- Adapt the existing “Happy Child” Program, creating actions for refugee children.
- Proposal to modify the legislation for the entry of migrants at the border so that they are not prevented from entering.
- As proposed by the group, there is the creation of a program within the Ministry of Women, Family, and Human Rights for refugee women and equal actions specific to indigenous groups.

- To eliminate risks and errors, the group recommends avoiding isolated actions such as that of the Federal Police in action in NGOs that focused on undocumented women and children.
- As new arrangements to meet the needs of the migrant population in Operation Acolhida, we have the implementation of psychological assistance offices and clinics on the streets to assist refugee children and women.

Ministry of Citizenship

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Scamper Tool

S	C	A	M	P	E	R
What should be replaced ?	How to combine actions in a coordinated way?	How to adapt actions to an existing reality?	What needs to be modified ?	What new proposals can be suggested?	What can we eliminate to avoid risks and errors?	What new arrangements can be implemented?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · elaboration of courses for the qualification of results · creation of university extension actions and activities · sensitize and instruct agents involved in the process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · “Criança Feliz” Program (already exists) - create actions for refugee children 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proposal to modify the legislation for the entry of migrants at the border, so that they are not prevented from entering 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Creation of a program within the Ministry of Women, Family and Human Rights for refugee women · equal actions specific to indigenous groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · isolated actions like that of the federal police 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of offices and psychological assistance clinics on the streets to assist refugee children and women

Armed Forces

- Coordination should be concentrated on logistics, but a permanent committee with the representatives of Acolhida and the external representatives might be permanent and transparent meeting minutes.
- A coordination committee should have a separate instrument to mobilize and create channels of communication, especially concerning public communication.
- Coordination schemes should consider ways to receive and organize policy to consider for compliance. With this, external relations of the coordination committee could be more smoothly driven when considering different institutional cultures and roles.
- International instruments of collaboration, observers, or policies should also be offered in a systematic way. As coordinators of the Acolhida Operation, the Armed Forces should not be responsible for all the connections associated with the reputation of the mission, as it serves the Brazilian interests towards other partners.
- If a general committee is installed to brief and discuss permanently the associated responsibilities and outcomes of the whole mission (not only the government and military branches), a tool can turn visible the various achievements in detail.
- Building data and permitting society participation in various forms. Individual, press and interest groups' participation should be guided considering international and local representation. Women and vulnerable communities are more affected if responsibilities are associated with the military only. Responsibility should also be shared.
- In terms of sharing responsibility, it should be considered that a committee could better propose various locus of representation in a hybrid and moving way.

Armed Forces

Scamper Tool

S	C	A	M	P	E	R
What should be replaced ?	How to combine actions in a coordinated way?	How to adapt actions to an existing reality?	What needs to be modified ?	What new proposals can be suggested?	What can we eliminate to avoid risks and errors?	What new arrangements can be implemented?
Coordination should be concentrated on logistic, but a permanent committee with the representatives of Acolhida and the external representatives might be permanent and transparent meetings minutes.	A coordination committee should have a separate instrument to mobilize and create channels of communication, specially concerning public communication.	Coordination scheme should consider ways to receive and organize policy to consider for compliance. With this, external relations of the coordination committee could be more smoothly driven when considering different institutional cultures and roles.	International instruments of collaboration, observers or policies should be offered also in a systematic way. As coordinators of the Acolhida Operation, the Armed Forces should not be responsible for all the connections associated to the reputation of the mission, as it serves the Brazilian interests towards other partners.	If a general committee is installed to brief and discuss permanently the associated responsibilities and outcomes of the whole mission (not only the government and military branches), a tool can turn it visible the various achievements in detail.	Building data and permitting society participation in various forms. Individual, press and interest groups participation should be guided considering international and local representation. Women and vulnerable communities are more affected if responsibilities are associated to military only. Responsibility should also be shared.	In terms of sharing responsibility, it should be considered that a committee could better propose various locus of representation in a hybrid and moving way.

Send feedback

Final Results

After the simulation was carried out in 4 working groups, represented by the UNHCR/NGO agencies, the Federal Police, the Ministry of Citizenship, and the Armed Forces, we returned to the collective forum to discuss the decisions made by the group and guided by the SCAMPER tool. The proposal in the collective forum was to discuss and expand the perspectives from the verification and knowledge of the activities and demands demonstrated by each of the agencies and, thus, corroborate with the construction of common elements for a solution in the interagency model, that is, in which all agencies involved, regardless of the interagency coordination model, are able to analyze the centralized process and its need to become decentralized.

The expectation of the simulation was to place the actors involved in bringing plausible solutions to an already found reality, seeking good practices, but adopting and suggesting new techniques, models, and ideal types to deal with the crisis inserted in the Acolhida Operation from the focus on female migrants, children and LGBTQIA+.

The solutions and suggestions, new proposals, and modifications in each of the agencies regarding their actions refer to the deepening of their competencies and adaptation of the processes to the reality and culture of the migrant population and to the demands of the groups addressed. Thus, within legality and regulations, there is a need to humanize the process and conduct the Operation in a way that respects the human and fundamental rights of the migrant population and the specificities of the group of women, children, and LGBTQI + as some of the most vulnerable groups in this population already affected by the issues that plague international migration.

Therefore, the discussions in the forum on the 28th, as well as the simulation activities on the 5th, affirmed the increasing emphasis on coordinated activities, inter-agency cooperation, greater understanding of the competencies of the organizations involved, especially on the aspect of complexity – with agencies at international and national levels (federal and federative levels). These coordinated actions must address the specificities of migrant groups with priority to fundamental rights, the process of internalization, the sharing of information and training, and the improvement of public agents to better guide the migrant population, as well as inserting it in a humanized and respectful manner.

In this stage, the groups returned from the breakout rooms to share their results and exposed other issues in addition to those made available in the SCAMPER tool. The moderators

presented the results, and the guests and the public had the opportunity to supplement with additional questions.

The simulation methodology and the combined use of tools allowed the invited representatives of agencies to reflect on their own actions and experiences on the field, as the Federal Police actor pointed out. In addition, he highlighted the reality of Pacaraima as a “complicated city located on a nervous border and in need of everything. The lack of infrastructure, material, and affection for them. A different reality from Haitians who migrated through an earthquake while Venezuelans are fleeing a humanitarian crisis and political persecution ”.

There is a production of different views by the Federal Police in this report. This difference brings the conception that migration is a constant, necessary movement and a survival factor for many people in the world. The institution, therefore, is "a representative of the State where the legal and the legitimate are approached in a human way, interacting with partners working together."

The centrality of the discussions started from the principle of overlapping vulnerabilities that migrants, especially women and children, suffer in their trajectories. It is necessary to analyze specific profiles and cases taking a different look in order to create sensitivity to ensure efficient responses.

Awareness-raising should be worked on with greater training for the various actors involved. One of the training proposals would be to involve universities in university extension projects as a way of attracting human resources as missionaries and volunteers and integrating local society. Actions like this could reduce episodes of xenophobia, for example, and also provide scientific support that would support agencies in different ways.

Proposed as permanent mechanisms for exchanging experiences, it would eliminate errors and allow better decision-making based on rational choices that would allow a better direction of actions. However, the improvement of communication channels would allow the elimination or reduction of risks to support a humanitarian mission of the size of Acolhida Operation.

The creation of permanent meetings in coordination with the ministries involved would also allow the generation of knowledge-based on daily experiences and the production of horizontal norms by people who experience reality. From the reports of the representative of the Federal Police and the representative of the American Development Foundation, we were able to understand that the temporal evolution is very important to analyze the case of the Brazil-Venezuela border.

With discussions focused on practice and reality, good practices could be reformulated, although the actors cited highlighted that the context of the pandemic is a watershed. The situation of the closed border allowed a change in the Operation's logistics, previously focused on the interiorization axis and now more focused on shelter.

Although the focus is on interiorization and today it focuses on housing, documentation is important to give access to individuals in transit. With the border blockade, flows are redirected through other porous routes, but without organs that act to facilitate regularization, a condition that leads more and more people to the street situation. Crisis coordination should also address this special situation.

In accordance with our event, the situation of women, children, adolescents, LGBTQIA+, and indigenous populations in transit was highlighted. In general, the conclusion is that existing policies need adaptations at different levels of the federation, as well as coordinating actions with public and private agents to assist these groups specifically.

In the discussion that was promoted about women, we highlight the increase of women in the global migratory flows. In our reality, the predominance is single-parent families, that is, women alone with their children. Women who have their vulnerability superimposed as a migrant and who still suffer from sexual violence and become victims of human trafficking.

The complementary propositions to those provided in SCAMPER continue to seek to strengthen and empower women with sustainable integration so that they achieve self-sufficiency and the resumption of dignity. The mechanism to be implemented should consider the inclusion of civil society organizations that target this specific point and in such a way that women themselves are at the center of decisions with active voices.

Regarding indigenous peoples, the guests identified four main groups. The Warao ethnic group is the most abundant and has a cultural characteristic of migration, which is not related to the beginning of the flow of Venezuelans, but which undergoes a considerable increase. They circulate within the cities of Boa Vista (RR), Pacaraima (RR), Manaus (AM) and Santarém (PA). The Public Prosecutor's Office requested priority vaccination for these peoples during the pandemic.

The major issue that permeates and hinders actions is cultural differences. Indigenous migrant women usually go out to ask for things on the streets for their living. In Brazil, they are treated in a marginalized way; they suffer xenophobia for an issue that, for them, would be normal. In this way, it is appropriate to think about specific, intercultural, and appropriate policies for indigenous peoples and the awareness of the actors who deal with the flow management.

Regarding children and adolescents, it was highlighted that, although they are minors, the way of acting is different between them. The entry of unaccompanied minors is recurrent, and the relationship of the homeland between Venezuelans is a problem that we have to deal with. Many arrive without their parents or with people with whom they have no family ties. In addition, many are undocumented and need to have their basic data identified in order to be asked for humanitarian support.

A very problematic issue for children without their legal representatives is the abandonment they suffer when they go through the process of internalization and go to other states. This fact highlights an existing gap and highlights an unstructured protection mechanism for these children, in which it should be adapted so that they are monitored from regularization to destination. In this case, the prioritization of documentation and confidentiality should be prioritized. The inclusion of refugee children in existing programs, such as Criança Feliz, could be a successful route.

The actors in this simulation point out that greater responsibilities could be attributed to agents of the Public Defender's Office in the sense of granting refugee status and promoting psychosocial interviews, promoting mechanisms to guarantee greater social assistance, and determining their permanence in Brazilian territory.

In relation to adolescents, the issue becomes more dramatic, as already pointed out, the relationship of father-power and distinct foot. A 15-year-old has greater autonomy in Venezuela and usually migrates alone. Upon arriving in Brazil and regularizing, he loses this autonomy because he is under the tutelage of the State. Action with this group also needs cultural adaptations and new forms of action.

The LGBTQIA + population appears subtly in the databases and is outside of targeted public policies that would avoid the sum of other vulnerability factors such as prejudice and exclusion. They are only given the right to migratory regularization with the assignment of their social names.

The issue of migratory regularization was a topic widely discussed, and all of them favored that the legislation allows the opening of the border, facilitating the entry by Operation Acolhida. The pandemic hindered this process as new routes were formed from the closure of borders. The Federal Police actor pointed out that the data system is not problematic but that the collection mechanism could be modified. They are collected differently for the flow of refugees and asylum seekers. For the latter, a greater number of documentation is required, attributing greater bureaucracy and complexity to the process.

The agent who represented the Armed Forces highlighted very important points in relation to the operability, interoperability, and governance structures of Acolhida Operation

Acolhida, which are under the responsibility of the Civil House, which, for the first time in Brazilian history, is commanded by an Army General.

She highlighted the great responsibility of actions in the Operation, but which works with the governance mechanism based on interagency cooperation, where public and private actors act together, not being the only ones responsible for the humanitarian mission. She points out that her work at the border is a previous prerogative together with the police forces.

Operation Acolhida is housed under a legal basis with the signing of Decree No. 9285, which recognized the vulnerability in Roraima due to the humanitarian crisis in Venezuela. From the recognition, the execution of this Humanitarian Logistics Task Force was justified.

The Operation is divided into three axes based, namely: border order, shelter, and interiorization. The second axis is where we perceive greater interagency work in the field.

But there are some points that need to be considered, such as:

- The organization and improvement of the structures that are coordinated with the civil house;
- Logistics is the main asset, so coordination should focus on the environmental issue, arrival, centralization of communication, and the transport of populations in transit;
- Promote periodic public meetings so that civil society can follow coordinated actions;
- Creation of a General Committee that is not only of the government to give efficiency to the governance;
- Create advanced protocols for sensitive information and identify which civil society can access;
- Draw terms of responsibility and make data more transparent.